

THE CURRENT DEVELOPMENT OF RELIGIOUS TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotatsiya. Ziyorat turizmining jadal rivojlanayotgan sohasi tufayli diniy maqsadli sayohatchilar soni ortib borayotganligi sababli, ziyoratning ma'nosini o'rganish zarurati tug'iladi. Muallif diniy turizm tarixini, uning dindorlar va butun jamiyat uchun ahamiyatini, shuningdek, turizmning ushbu turining asosiy turlarini ko'rib chiqadi. Maqolada diniy turizmning hayotning turli jabhalariga, jumladan, ijtimoiy-madaniy va iqtisodiy oqibatlarga ta'siri ham muhokama qilinadi. Taqdim etilgan sharh o'quvchilarga zamonaviy dunyoda diniy turizmning qiymati va xilma-xilligini yaxshiroq tushunishga yordam beradi. Ushbu asarda diniy turizm uch qismdan iborat bo'lib, ularning har biri o'ziga xos tushuntirishga ega. Birinchi qismda ziyoratchi va ziyorat turizmi belgilab qo'yilgan bo'lsa, keyingi bosqichda boshqa turlardan ko'ra diniy turizmni tanlagan sayyohlar motivlari va nihoyat, O'zbekistondagi diniy turizm bilan bog'liq hozirgi vaziyat mavjud. Demak, material ziyoratchilar va O'zbekiston bilan ziyorat turizmi haqida keng qamrovli tushuntirishlar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ziyorat, diniy turizm, din, islom, ziyorat, o'zbekiston, turizm, tarix, madaniyat, ma'naviyat.

Аннотация. С ростом числа путешественников, преследующих религиозные цели, в связи с быстрым развитием паломнического туризма возникает необходимость в изучении значения паломничества. В данной работе религиозный туризм рассматривается и представлен в трёх частях, каждая из которых имеет своё объяснение. В первой части даётся определение паломничества и паломнического туризма; далее рассматриваются мотивы туристов, выбирающих религиозный туризм среди других видов; в последней части описывается современное состояние религиозного туризма в Узбекистане. Таким образом, материал предлагает всестороннее объяснение феномена паломничества и паломнического туризма на примере Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: паломник, религиозный туризм, религия, ислам, паломничество.

Abstract. As the number of travelers with religious purpose is rising due to rapidly developing field of pilgrimage tourism, there is a need to investigate the meaning of pilgrimage. In this work, the religious tourism is explained and represented in three parts, each of which has its own clarification. In the first part the pilgrim and the pilgrimage tourism are defined, next there are motivations of tourists chosen religious tourism over other types and, lastly, the current situation with religious tourism in Uzbekistan. Hence, the material offers a comprehensive explanation on pilgrims and pilgrimage tourism with Uzbekistan given as an example country.

Keywords: pilgrim, religious tourism, religion, Islam, pilgrimage.

Introduction

In the modern world where the field of tourism is on the peak of developing, particularly religious tourism, as the number of people desiring pilgrimage experience is rising in various countries. Remarkably, this type of tourism is thought to be one of the earliest, since it existed for

more than two millennia. As the decades flew by, pilgrimage to sacred places spread all around the world and became accessible not only to wealthy oligarchy but also to middle class individuals. Therefore, there is a necessity to take a broad view on religious tourism itself, to obtain a deeper understanding in motives of pilgrims. This paper focuses on explaining pilgrimage tourism and its implication on Uzbekistan, by, firstly defining a pilgrim and religious travelling, then analyzing reasons of visiting sacred sites and finally, demonstrating the situation with pilgrimage in Uzbekistan.

Discussions

The term of pilgrimage tourism is much more than simply travelling to different parts of the world and praying, religious tourism refers to peace of an individual. According to two researchers – Juraeva and Akhrorova - “Although the word “Pilgrimage” is typically associated with religion, it can fulfil certain individuals’ needs beyond spiritual reasons while vast majority of sacred way walkers do not consider themselves under the name of “Tourist”, but “Pilgrim”.” (2023). Furthermore, as it was stated by Serrallonga, “pilgrimage is not seen as an ending point but as a starting one, it helps participants to find the path to inner peace, but they must continue working (or walking) this path.” (2020). Consequently, the meaning of “pilgrimage” is quite comprehensive to be explained as “praying” or “religious rituals” only. It is believed that during a pilgrimage an individual undergoes a process of altering, in which he or she reaches a peak of calmness. As it was claimed by Greenia in 2018, “Being a doctor, husband, class clown, nun, flirt or cop are all social roles with a heavy roster of behaviors and boundaries, specific ways to speak and act and dress and consume and interact with one's environment. All those “secular” off-trail forms of ego definition tend to melt away while on pilgrimage”. So, no matter the gender, status, ethnicity, race or personal traits – everyone is egalitarian in pilgrimage.

Results

To understand the concept of religious tourism in more depth, it is important to analyze motivations that push people to conduct a pilgrimage, which vary from seeking peace to purchasing religious items. According to the table presented by Tahani Hassan, motivations of pilgrimage tourism are divided into three dimensions - religious, social and cultural and shopping. The conducted survey has demonstrated that the majority of pilgrims were driven by the desire to fulfill their religious needs (2023). Additionally, the research by Johnmeyer and Xu suggests that travelers visit religious sites not only due to spirituality, but also due to the interest of a culture, nature or history (2022). Thus, although, the majority of pilgrims visit holy sites due to spiritual desires, a significant number of other religious tourists come out of curiosity or to purchase particular goods.

Uzbekistan is a unique country, as it played a vital role in the Silk Road trade – where decisive number of cultures has exchanged not only goods and traditions, but also religions and sacred rituals. As a result, the country is enriched with mosques and churches of different religions. The most followed religion in Uzbekistan is Islam, even though, there are people of other religions living in the country as well. Before Islam, residents of modern Uzbekistan used to follow Zoroastrianism, until in the seventh century has begun a rapid spread of Islam. Religious tourism in Uzbekistan is gaining momentum as the country has a number of holy sites and in the process of constructing more mosques. As it was written in the article by Tadjibayev, “Bukhara has about 360 mosques and 80 madrasahs and owns title “The star of Islamic world”, as the Bukhara is one of the 7 holy cities, such as Mecca, Medina, Baghdad, Damascus, Jerusalem and Mazari-Sharif.” (n.d.). Certainly, there rises a question, why Bukhara is thought to be a religious city of Uzbekistan

and not Tashkent or Samarkand, that have numerous pilgrimage sites. In order to ascertain this point, as it was suggested by the same researcher, there is a legend, that Bahouddin Naqshband had a dream before his trip to Mecca, where the prophet Ibragim told him he saw three rays – one from Mecca, another from Medina and the third one from Bukhara (Tadjibayev, n.d.). Therefore, Bukhara is known as the most common destination among other Uzbekistan cities in the Muslim world. In addition, other researchers have suggested that, “resulting from the availability of holy pilgrimage possibilities there is opportunity to create many pilgrimage sites and itineraries. As examples: “Homeland of Imam Al-Bukhary”, “Seven Saints of Bukhara”, “Pilgrimage based on “Holy Bukhara.”” (Navruz-Zoda et al., 2019). Hence, the growing flow of religious tourists in Uzbekistan is reasonable as the country has a plethora of holy sites.

Conclusion

To conclude, currently developing field of pilgrimage tourism has already gained attention of the great number of travelers and is influencing economy of a particular country, in this case – Uzbekistan, in the most beneficial way. As it was explained, pilgrimage has a comprehensive meaning and an extensive implication on Uzbekistan. Although, this work has covered the explanation of religious tourism, its forms and motivations and, lastly, pilgrimage sites in Uzbekistan. There is, perhaps, a necessity to do further research on religious rituals and norms, rules of behaving in sacred places.

REFERENCES

1. Greenia, G. (2018). What is Pilgrimage? *Arts & Sciences Articles*. <https://doi.org/https://core.ac.uk/works/13919326>
2. Hassan, T., Carvache-Franco, M., Carvache-Franco, O., & Carvache-Franco, W. (2023). Sociodemographic relationships of motivations, satisfaction, and loyalty in religious tourism: A study of the pilgrimage to the city Mecca. *PLoS ONE* 18(3) Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0283720>
3. Johnmeyer, C., & Xu, S. (2022). Proposing A Conceptual Model for Understanding the Transformative Experiences of Pilgrimage Tourists. *Travel and Tourism Research Association: Advancing Tourism Research Globally*. Doi: <https://doi.org/https://core.ac.uk/works/124885167>
4. Juraeva, S., & Akhrorova, N. (2023). The effect of the religious pilgrimage on social norms and identity. *International conference “History, cultural heritage and tourism opportunities of the Silk Road peoples (Past and Present)”*, 129-134
5. Navruz-Zoda, B., Ibragimov, N., & Rakhmanov, A. (2019). Perspectives on the Improvement as a Destination for Multi-Confessional Self-Organised Pilgrims. *International Journal of Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage*: Vol. 7: Iss. 4, Article 11, 94-95 Doi: <https://doi.org/10.21427/ba9h-bn89>
6. Serrallonga, S. A. (2020). Pilgrim’s Motivations: A Theoretical Approach to Pilgrimage as a Peacebuilding Tool. *International Journal of Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage*. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.21427/zhad-9555>
7. Tadjibayev, S. (n.d.) Особенности паломнического туризма в Узбекистане [Features of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan]

